

Right Ventricular Myxoma in a Patient With Ebstein's Anomaly: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cardiac myxomas are the most frequent primary heart tumors. Their presence in right heart chambers is uncommon, and their association with Ebstein's anomaly is extremely rare.

Case presentation: A 24-year-old man with a history of Ebstein-Carpentier type B anomaly, recurrent arrhythmias, and various device-related complications was diagnosed with an intracardiac mass consistent with a right ventricular myxoma during echocardiographic evaluation. Surgical resection was recommended, but the patient declined due to the surgical risk and opted for conservative treatment.

Discussion: The coexistence of Ebstein's anomaly and right ventricular myxoma is poorly documented. Detection of intracardiac masses in these patients can significantly influence therapeutic decisions.

Conclusions: Structural surveillance in patients with congenital heart disease such as Ebstein's anomaly is essential to detect coexisting intracardiac tumors.

KEYWORDS: Myxoma, Ebstein's anomaly, intracardiac mass, ecocardiography, pacemaker, congenital heart disease.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiac myxomas are the most common primary tumors of the heart, with a preference for the left atrium. Their presence in right heart chambers, especially the right ventricle, is rare. Ebstein's anomaly is an uncommon congenital malformation of the tricuspid valve that may lead to severe hemodynamic dysfunction and arrhythmias. The coexistence of both conditions is exceptional and rarely described in the literature.

II. CASE REPORT

A 24-year-old male with a diagnosis of Carpentier type B Ebstein's anomaly since childhood experienced multiple episodes of arrhythmias. At the age of 15, he underwent ablation of an accessory pathway and continued on antiarrhythmic therapy due to paroxysmal atrial fibrillation.

At 19, he was hospitalized for supraventricular tachycardia after voluntarily discontinuing his treatment. A 24-hour Holter revealed pauses up to 2.1 seconds, leading to the indication for permanent pacemaker implantation.

Due to persistent exertional dyspnea and palpitations, a pre-surgical protocol for valve repair was initiated. Transthoracic echocardiography showed severe tricuspid regurgitation and borderline right ventricular function. A stress test using the Bruce protocol confirmed NYHA class II symptoms. A second ablation was performed for documented reentrant tachycardia, and surgical tricuspid valve plasty was scheduled.

During follow-up, the patient experienced conduction disturbances, lead dislocation, and cutaneous changes suggestive of device-related infection, although no causative microorganism was isolated. He was treated empirically and

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remained on propafenone until 2023, when he presented with pacemaker dysfunction and symptomatic arrhythmias. Electrical cardioversion was performed, and the capture threshold was adjusted. The patient later underwent valve plasty using the Connell technique and reimplantation of a new pacemaker.

An ischemic transient attack was reported in the months following surgery. Subsequently, three additional episodes of pacemaker dysfunction occurred: the first due to atrioventricular block with wide QRS and dislocation of the atrial lead, the second due to complete heart block, and the third related to a cutaneous lesion over the implant site with non-purulent serohematic discharge and local swelling. A hypersensitivity reaction to pacemaker components (nickel and titanium) was confirmed, requiring explantation and replacement with a PTFE-coated lead.

During the pre-discharge evaluation, a hyperechoic area was detected in the posteroinferior wall of the right ventricle, and a decision was made to initiate an intracardiac mass approach. Diagnostic tests included blood cultures, which were negative; transthoracic echocardiography with sulfur hexafluoride-based contrast showed a pedunculated, mobile mass measuring 19×16 mm adherent to the myocardium; and cardiac computed tomography angiography showed a contrast-enhanced nodular lesion consistent with a right ventricular myxoma. Although surgical removal was recommended, the preoperative risk was very high; therefore, after the case was discussed, the patient declined further invasive treatment.

Figures 1. Contrast-enhanced transthoracic echocardiography with sulfur hexafluoride showing a pedunculated mass in the right ventricle with ball-valve motion.

Figures 2 and 3. Axial and sagittal views from cardiac CT showing a well-circumscribed, pedunculated mass in the right ventricle, located in the posteroinferior apical region, measuring 18×16 mm, with heterogeneous density.

III. DISCUSSION

Cardiac myxomas are benign tumors that account for approximately 50% of all primary cardiac neoplasms. They are most frequently located in the left atrium, followed by the right atrium, and only rarely in the ventricles; therefore, right ventricular location is exceptionally rare. Most cases are sporadic, although familial forms with autosomal dominant inheritance exist. Clinical manifestations vary depending on the size, location, and mobility of the tumor and may be asymptomatic or present with obstructive, embolic, or constitutional symptoms. In the right cardiac chambers, signs are usually related to right heart failure, syncope, dyspnea, palpitations, or peripheral oedema. A pedunculated, mobile mass prolapsed through the tricuspid valve may mimic valvular disease. Although histologically benign, myxomas can cause serious complications, such as sudden cardiac death, pulmonary embolism, or infective endocarditis, particularly in patients with intracardiac devices or a surgical history.

The coexistence of right ventricular myxoma and Ebstein's anomaly is extremely rare, with only two documented case reports worldwide. One involved an incidental finding with no hemodynamic impact, and the other described valvular obstruction exacerbated by the tumor. Both diagnoses were based on echocardiography and confirmed histologically.

This case is particularly relevant due to three characteristics: the unusual location of the myxoma, its coexistence with complex congenital heart disease, and the diagnostic challenge posed by overlapping symptoms and complications related to pacemaker rejection. These characteristics highlight the need for a high index of suspicion and meticulous echocardiographic evaluation in patients with Ebstein's anomaly, even in the absence of new symptoms. Transthoracic and, when necessary, transesophageal echocardiography can identify intracardiac masses, their mobility, insertion site, and morphology. Cardiac computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) help further characterize the lesion. While histopathology

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confirms the diagnosis, the clinical and imaging context is usually sufficient to proceed with treatment.

Although surgical resection is the treatment of choice due to the embolic and obstructive risk of myxomas, the decision must be individualized. In this patient, having undergone prior valve replacement, with subsequent tissue fibrosis, as well as multiple rejection and repositioning of the pacemaker, and the technical complexity due to the location of the mass, there was a high preoperative risk with a high probability of death. Therefore, after a case review and in accordance with the patient's right to autonomy, conservative treatment with close monitoring and follow-up was chosen.

CONCLUSIONS

The coexistence of Ebstein's anomaly and right ventricular myxoma is a rare but clinically relevant combination. Early identification of intracardiac masses in patients with congenital heart disease can modify treatment and improve prognosis. Structural imaging surveillance is essential, even in patients without new symptoms.

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